

1. What is your current occupation? *

Mark only one oval.

- Industrial or freelance professional
- Academic or industrial researcher
- Undergraduate/graduate student
- Other: _____

2. Which of the following best describes your primary job role? *

Mark only one oval.

- Development
- Testing
- Project Management
- Other: _____

3. How many years of experience do you have with your primary job role? (Please input a number, decimals okay) *

4. Current country/area of residence? *

Mark only one oval.

- Afghanistan (AFG)
- Albania (ALB)
- Algeria (DZA)
- American Samoa (ASM)
- Andorra (AND)
- Angola (AGO)
- Anguilla (AIA)
- Antigua and Barbuda (ATG)
- Argentina (ARG)
- Armenia (ARM)
- Aruba (ABW)
- Australia (AUS)
- Austria (AUT)
- Azerbaijan (AZE)
- Bahamas, The (BHM)
- Bahrain (BHR)
- Bangladesh (BGD)
- Barbados (BRB)
- Belarus (BLR)
- Belgium (BEL)
- Belize (BLZ)
- Benin (BEN)
- Bermuda (BMU)
- Bhutan (BTN)
- Bolivia (BOL)
- Bosnia and Herzegovina (BIH)
- Botswana (BWA)
- Brazil (BRA)
- British Virgin Islands (VGB)
- Brunei (BRN)
- Bulgaria (BGR)
- Burkina Faso (BFA)

- Burma (MMR)
- Burundi (BDI)
- Cabo Verde (CPV)
- Cambodia (KHM)
- Cameroon (CMR)
- Canada (CAN)
- Cayman Islands (CYM)
- Central African Republic (CAF)
- Chad (TCD)
- Chile (CHL)
- China (CHN)
- Colombia (COL)
- Comoros (COM)
- Congo, Democratic Republic of the (COD)
- Congo, Republic of the (COG)
- Cook Islands (COK)
- Costa Rica (CRI)
- Cote d'Ivoire (CIV)
- Croatia (HRV)
- Cuba (CUB)
- Curacao (CUW)
- Cyprus (CYP)
- Czech Republic (CZE)
- Denmark (DNK)
- Djibouti (DJI)
- Dominica (DMA)
- Dominican Republic (DOM)
- Ecuador (ECU)
- Egypt (EGY)
- El Salvador (SLV)
- Equatorial Guinea (GNQ)
- Eritrea (ERI)
- Estonia (EST)
- Ethiopia (ETH)
- Falkland Islands (Islas Malvinas) (FLK)

- Faroe Islands (FRO)
- Fiji (FJI)
- Finland (FIN)
- France (FRA)
- French Polynesia (PYF)
- Gabon (GAB)
- Gambia, The (GMB)
- Georgia (GEO)
- Germany (DEU)
- Ghana (GHA)
- Gibraltar (GIB)
- Greece (GRC)
- Greenland (GRL)
- Grenada (GRD)
- Guam (GUM)
- Guatemala (GTM)
- Guernsey (GGY)
- Guinea-Bissau (GNB)
- Guinea (GIN)
- Guyana (GUY)
- Haiti (HTI)
- Honduras (HND)
- Hong Kong (HKG)
- Hungary (HUN)
- Iceland (ISL)
- India (IND)
- Indonesia (IDN)
- Iran (IRN)
- Iraq (IRQ)
- Ireland (IRL)
- Isle of Man (IMN)
- Israel (ISR)
- Italy (ITA)
- Jamaica (JAM)
- Japan (JPN)

- Jersey (JEY)
- Jordan (JOR)
- Kazakhstan (KAZ)
- Kenya (KEN)
- Kiribati (KIR)
- Korea, North (PRK)
- Korea, South (KOR)
- Kosovo (KSV)
- Kuwait (KWT)
- Kyrgyzstan (KGZ)
- Laos (LAO)
- Latvia (LVA)
- Lebanon (LBN)
- Lesotho (LSO)
- Liberia (LBR)
- Libya (LBY)
- Liechtenstein (LIE)
- Lithuania (LTU)
- Luxembourg (LUX)
- Macau (MAC)
- Macedonia (MKD)
- Madagascar (MDG)
- Malawi (MWI)
- Malaysia (MYS)
- Maldives (MDV)
- Mali (MLI)
- Malta (MLT)
- Marshall Islands (MHL)
- Mauritania (MRT)
- Mauritius (MUS)
- Mexico (MEX)
- Micronesia, Federated States of (FSM)
- Moldova (MDA)
- Monaco (MCO)
- Mongolia (MNG)

- Montenegro (MNE)
- Morocco (MAR)
- Mozambique (MOZ)
- Namibia (NAM)
- Nepal (NPL)
- Netherlands (NLD)
- New Caledonia (NCL)
- New Zealand (NZL)
- Nicaragua (NIC)
- Nigeria (NGA)
- Niger (NER)
- Niue (NIU)
- Northern Mariana Islands (MNP)
- Norway (NOR)
- Oman (OMN)
- Pakistan (PAK)
- Palau (PLW)
- Panama (PAN)
- Papua New Guinea (PNG)
- Paraguay (PRY)
- Peru (PER)
- Philippines (PHL)
- Poland (POL)
- Portugal (PRT)
- Puerto Rico (PRI)
- Qatar (QAT)
- Romania (ROU)
- Russia (RUS)
- Rwanda (RWA)
- Saint Kitts and Nevis (KNA)
- Saint Lucia (LCA)
- Saint Martin (MAF)
- Saint Pierre and Miquelon (SPM)
- Saint Vincent and the Grenadines (VCT)
- Samoa (WSM)

- San Marino (SMR)
- Sao Tome and Principe (STP)
- Saudi Arabia (SAU)
- Senegal (SEN)
- Serbia (SRB)
- Seychelles (SYC)
- Sierra Leone (SLE)
- Singapore (SGP)
- Sint Maarten (SXM)
- Slovakia (SVK)
- Slovenia (SVN)
- Solomon Islands (SLB)
- Somalia (SOM)
- South Africa (ZAF)
- South Sudan (SSD)
- Spain (ESP)
- Sri Lanka (LKA)
- Sudan (SDN)
- Suriname (SUR)
- Swaziland (SWZ)
- Sweden (SWE)
- Switzerland (CHE)
- Syria (SYR)
- Taiwan (TWN)
- Tajikistan (TJK)
- Tanzania (TZA)
- Thailand (THA)
- Timor-Leste (TLS)
- Togo (TGO)
- Tonga (TON)
- Trinidad and Tobago (TTO)
- Tunisia (TUN)
- Turkey (TUR)
- Turkmenistan (TKM)
- Tuvalu (TUV)

- Uganda (UGA)
- Ukraine (UKR)
- United Arab Emirates (ARE)
- United Kingdom (GBR)
- United States (USA)
- Uruguay (URY)
- Uzbekistan (UZB)
- Vanuatu (VUT)
- Venezuela (VEN)
- Vietnam (VNM)
- Virgin Islands (VGB)
- West Bank (WBG)
- Yemen (YEM)
- Zambia (ZMB)
- Zimbabwe (ZWE)

5. About your current project: How many people are involved in your team? *

Mark only one oval.

- 1-5
- 6-10
- 11-20
- 21-40
- Other: _____

6. Your primary programming language? *

Mark only one oval.

- C/C++
- C#
- Go
- Java
- JavaScript
- Kotlin
- Objective-C
- Perl
- PHP
- Python
- R
- Ruby
- Rust
- Scala
- SQL
- Swift
- TypeScript
- Visual Basic
- Other: _____

7. How knowledgeable are you about information security? *

Mark only one oval.

- Not at all
- Slightly
- Moderately
- Very
- Extremely

8. Do you have experience with smart contracts? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Smart Contract Specific Experience

9. For about how many years have you been developing smart contracts? (Please input a number, decimals okay) *

10. What best describes the primary blockchain platform you currently work on? *

Mark only one oval.

Public blockchain

Consortium blockchain

Private blockchain

Other: _____

11. What best describes the blockchains you currently work on? (Please select all that apply) *

Tick all that apply.

Aeternity

Bitcoin

Ethereum

EOS

Hyperledger Fabric

RSK

Stellar

Tezos

Waves

Other: _____

14. About your team: Primary life cycle model? *

Mark only one oval.

- Waterfall
- Iterative
- Agile
- Other: _____

15. How often does your team release a new version of smart contracts over the past two years? *

Mark only one oval.

- Never
- Annually
- Quarterly
- Monthly
- Weekly
- Daily

Smart Contract: Security Awareness

16. Have you ever experienced a security issue with the smart contracts your team has developed? (Please select all that apply) *

Tick all that apply.

- Yes, we experienced a security breach.
- Yes, a vulnerability in shipped code was discovered.
- Yes, a vulnerability in unshipped code was discovered.
- No, we have never experienced a security issue.
- I don't know or prefer not to answer.

Other: _____

17. Which resources do you use to gain security knowledge for smart contracts?
(Please select all that apply) *

Tick all that apply.

- Research Papers
- Official Forums of Blockchain Platforms
- Latest News (e.g., coindesk)
- Question and Answer Websites (e.g., Stack Overflow)
- Blockchain Security Companies (e.g., OpenZeppelin)

Other: _____

Please kindly rate each statement, with respect to your experience with the primary blockchain you specified above.

attacks on smart
contracts deployed to
blockchains.

25. What other strategies (if any) does your team use to ensure smart contract security? (Optional)

26. How frequently does your team use each of the following techniques to ensure the security and privacy of smart contracts? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Very Rarely	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Very Often	I don't know.
Input validation	<input type="radio"/>					
Bytecode hardening	<input type="radio"/>					
Access control enforcement	<input type="radio"/>					
Avoid improper use of functions (e.g., DelegateCall())	<input type="radio"/>					

27. What other techniques (if any) does your team use to ensure smart contract security? (Optional)

28. How frequently does your team use each of the following tools to ensure the security and privacy of smart contracts? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Very Rarely	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Very Often	I don't know.
Formal verification tool (e.g., Boogie)	<input type="radio"/>					
Fuzzer (e.g., ILF and Echidna)	<input type="radio"/>					
Reverse engineering tool	<input type="radio"/>					
Security plugin in IDE (e.g., Remix)	<input type="radio"/>					
Mythril	<input type="radio"/>					
Oyente	<input type="radio"/>					
SmartCheck	<input type="radio"/>					
Slither	<input type="radio"/>					

29. What other tools (if any) does your team use to ensure smart contract security? (Optional)

30. What are the limitations of security tools for smart contracts that you are aware of? (Optional)

32. Could you please brainstorm an ideal tool for ensuring smart contract security?
It can be as fancy as whatever you can think of. (Optional)

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